

Review

Machine Learning on the Frontlines of Air Pollution and Public Health: Revealing the Connection with Hospital Admissions

Farzaneh Abedian Aval ¹, Sina Ataee ¹

¹ CESAM & Department of Environment and Planning, University of Aveiro, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal; f.abedian@ua.pt (F.A.A.); sinaataee@ua.pt (S.A.); btavaress35@ua.pt (B.T.S.); diogojlopes@ua.pt (D.L.); miranda@ua.pt (A.I.M.)

² Institute of Telecommunications, University of Aveiro, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal

³ Centro de Ciências e Tecnologias Nucleares (C²TN), Department of Nuclear Sciences and Engineering (DECN), Instituto Superior Técnico, Universidade de Lisboa, 2695-066 Bobadela, Portugal; vania.martins@ctn.tecnico.ulisboa.pt

* Correspondence: behrouz.nemati@ua.pt (B.N.); helder.relvas@ua.pt (H.R.)

Abstract

Air pollution is a major factor influencing hospital admissions worldwide, highlighting the need for robust predictive tools to support healthcare planning and public health measures. Machine learning (ML) has been widely employed to simulate the intricate relationships between pollution and health outcomes. This paper examines publications indexed in the Scopus database, from 2010 to 2024 focusing on using ML techniques to forecast outcomes related to air pollution and hospital admissions. A bibliometric study of the 89 identified papers was also conducted to determine dominant research themes, commonly employed methodologies, and the geographical distribution of publications. The results indicate that research activity increased notably after 2020, with the United States of America, China, and Brazil contributing the highest number of publications. Moreover, the findings indicate that approximately 83% of the reviewed research applied predictive models appropriately, suggesting that ML techniques can effectively forecast healthcare outcomes. Random Forest was the most frequently used method (33 studies), followed by Neural Networks (18 studies). Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) algorithm, although less frequent, showed the highest reported accuracy, with values ranging from 87% to 95%. The most studied pollutants were particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), and coarse particulate matter (PM₁₀). Demographic and meteorological data were the most frequently used complementary (71% and 65%, respectively), followed by temporal (46%) and socioeconomic factors (20%). The combination of several variable categories not only enhanced understanding of how environmental exposure affects health outcomes but also improved the accuracy and reliability of the reviewed ML models.

Academic Editor: Changqing Lin

Received: 28 October 2025

Revised: 12 December 2025

Accepted: 20 December 2025

Published: 23 December 2025

Copyright: © 2025 by the authors.

Licensee MDPI, Basel, Switzerland.

This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the [Creative Commons Attribution \(CC BY\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) license.

Keywords: public health; environmental exposure; predictive models; healthcare planning; data-driven health prediction

1. Introduction

Air pollution, which has increased due to environmental changes and shifts in climate, affects many cities around the world [1,2]. Being exposed to particulate matter (PM) has been linked with millions of deaths and is recognized as a major factor related to health problems globally [3,4]. Although actions have been taken in different regions to reduce

pollution, the levels of pollutants in several cities' world big cities such as São Paulo [5,6] and Nanjing [7,8], remain above the suggested limits set by global and national authorities. This persistent challenge underscores the need for effective approaches to manage air pollution [9,10]. Long-term exposure to air pollution has been associated with respiratory and cardiovascular diseases, including lung conditions, heart disease, strokes, and cancers affecting the respiratory system [11–14]. Short-term exposure has also been connected to symptoms such as sneezing, headaches, dizziness, and eye irritation [15–19]. In some instances, the severity of these symptoms has resulted in individuals seeking care at health facilities, and in certain cases, hospitalization has been required. In addition to physical effects, some studies have indicated a potential association between polluted air, outdoor comfort [20], mental well-being [21–23], as well as burden of low birth weight [24]. Mitigating these impacts requires timely access to reliable air quality data and the implementation of effective protective measures [25,26]. As a result, numerous regions have increasingly deployed systems dedicated to air quality measurement and monitoring [27,28].

A thorough analysis of the link between air pollution and hospital admissions, particularly for individuals with respiratory and cardiovascular conditions, is considered important in the context of public health and environmental management [29,30]. By examining hospital visits and inpatient records during periods of increased air pollutant concentrations, critical exposure times and vulnerable groups can be identified. This information may support the development of forecasting systems that estimate healthcare demand, allow healthcare facilities to adjust resource allocation accordingly and can assist policymakers in designing targeted interventions and environmental regulations [31,32]. Early warning systems may also be established for at-risk populations, helping to initiate timely preventive actions when air quality deteriorates [33,34]. The results from these investigations could be used in long-term planning, including improvements in urban design and investment in cleaner technologies. They may also contribute to raising public awareness of pollution-related health risks and promoting protective actions among residents. Overall, connecting air quality indicators with hospital admission data provides a useful approach for informing decision-making and improving health outcomes in affected communities [35–37].

In this regard, to examine the connection between air pollution and hospital admissions, various traditional statistical and epidemiological techniques have been applied. Common methods include multiple linear regression [38], time series approaches like Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) [39], general equilibrium models [40], and studies based on spatiotemporal correlations [41]. In addition, panel data techniques and non-parametric approaches, such as covariance-based models, have been employed. While these approaches have been applied in many studies, they usually depend on fixed assumptions and may not fully capture the nonlinearities and complex associations among variables [42–44]. In recent years, more attention has been given to the use of machine learning (ML) for addressing such limitations. ML algorithms such as Random Forest [45], Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) [46], Support Vector Machines (SVM) [47], and deep learning approaches have been adopted to model the links between air quality parameters and health-related data [48,49]. The use of ML enables the detection of underlying patterns, management of large-scale datasets, and more accurate outcome prediction, which can support better assessments of the health impacts related to air pollution. The importance of this methodological shift lies in its ability to overcome the limitations of traditional approaches and offer more reliable insights into the health effects of pollution. Nevertheless, despite these advantages, relatively few studies have systematically applied ML techniques to hospital admission data linked to air pollution, creating a clear research gap

that underscores the need for a comprehensive review to consolidate existing evidence and guide future investigations [50–52].

This review paper focuses on studies that explored the relationship between air pollution and hospital admissions with ML techniques. The purpose of the review is to describe the existing methods, list the frequently applied algorithms, point out the main health outcomes examined, and assess both the advantages and weaknesses of the current research trends. By presenting a structured summary of the literature, this work intends to provide guidance for future investigations and assist in the development of more precise and data-oriented approaches for estimating and managing the health effects linked to air pollution.

To guide the scope and analytical focus of this review, a set of research questions was formulated. These questions were developed based on identified gaps in the literature and are aligned with the aim of exploring the intersection of ML, air pollution, and hospital admissions. Specifically, the questions address the current bibliometric status of the field, the influence of specific air pollutants and demographic variables on model performance, the effectiveness of different ML algorithms, and the main methodological trends and innovations over the past decade. Additionally, future prospects are considered to outline potential directions for research and application.

1. What is the current bibliometric status of literature in this field?
2. What are the most effective ML algorithms in this field, and how do they compare in terms of performance?
3. What are the most used air pollutants and complementary variables influencing the performance of ML models in this field?
4. What are the key methodological limitations, trends, and future prospects in ML-based studies on air pollution and hospital admissions?

The questions outlined above are examined in detail throughout the subsequent sections, where relevant studies are reviewed and key findings are synthesized.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Literature Search Strategy

A structured search approach was applied to identify original research articles focusing on the use of ML in the context of hospital admissions and air pollution exposure (see Figure 1). The Scopus database was selected due to its broad subject coverage across scientific disciplines. A combination of Boolean operators and controlled keyword fields (TITLE-ABS-KEY) was used to build the search query. This query included ML-related terms (e.g., “artificial intelligence”, “machine learning”, “deep learning”, “random forest”, “support vector machine”) alongside health-related keywords (e.g., “hospitalization”, “emergency department”, “asthma admission”) and environmental exposure terms (e.g., “air pollution”, “PM_{2.5}”, “NO₂”, “particulate matter”). This search process resulted in an initial identification of 304 publications.

The identified records underwent a filtering process based on predefined criteria. As shown in Figure 1, first, publications were restricted to 2010–2024, limited to original research articles and written in English, resulting in 178 articles. After title and abstract screening, 78 were excluded. A full-text review of the remaining 100 studies led to the exclusion of 11 additional papers due to its insufficient relevance, leaving 89 articles for the final analysis. Although this systematic selection process ensured methodological consistency, it also introduced certain inherent limitations. Nevertheless, Scopus is one of the most comprehensive and widely used abstract and citation databases, offering broad coverage of high-quality scientific literature. We believe that even if some non-English

studies or articles published in journals not indexed by Scopus were not captured in our search, their absence is unlikely to affect the main conclusions of this review. Given that the majority of reputable research in the field of air pollution and health is indexed in databases such as Scopus, the key findings of this study are expected to remain robust and reliable.

Figure 1. Search Strategy and Study Selection Framework.

2.2. Database and Software

Following the final selection of 89 eligible articles, the bibliographic information of these studies was exported from the Scopus database in CSV format. The exported dataset included key metadata such as publication year, country of origin, subject area classification, source title, and provided keywords. This dataset was organized and cleaned to ensure consistency in fields such as author keywords and country names. Standardization procedures were applied to address spelling variations and duplicates in keyword entries. The cleaned dataset was imported into VOSviewer software (version 1.6.20), a bibliometric visualization tool for keyword-based analysis. The software settings were configured to detect keyword occurrence and clustering.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Bibliometric Status

3.1.1. Year-Wise Distribution of Publications

The annual distribution of scientific publications provides valuable insight into the evolving role of ML at the nexus of air pollution and hospital admissions (Figure 2). Between 2010 and 2019, the number of studies remained low and irregular (0–3), suggesting that ML was not widely applied. From 2020 onward, a gradual increase in publications was observed, reaching a peak of 23 in 2024. This trend may be associated with the broader adoption of data-driven methods to examine the effects of air pollution on health, particularly in relation to hospital admissions. It indicates that ML has been increasingly utilized as a methodological approach in this line of research.

Figure 2. Annual distribution of scientific publications from 2010 to 2024.

3.1.2. Contribution of the Countries

The geographical distribution of publications indicates that ML has been used to investigate the association between air pollution and hospital admissions in a variety of countries. As shown in Figure 3, the United States of America (USA) was linked to the most studies, followed by China and Brazil (Brazil), respectively, with 30, 18 and 11 publications. Italy and South Korea each recorded 8 publications, and Australia was involved with 6. Iran and the United Kingdom contributed 5 studies, while India accounted for 4. France and Spain were each represented by 3 publications. Countries including Canada, Greece, South Africa, Taiwan, and Turkey reported 2 publications. All other contributing countries were represented by only one study each. These differences might be caused by differences in data access, research priorities, or funding availability. This pattern indicates that predictive approaches in this field have been gradually applied across different regions, with increasing participation from both developed and developing countries.

3.1.3. Scientific Output by Subject Area

The distribution of subject areas indicates the multidisciplinary scope of ML-based research on air pollution and hospital admissions (Figure 4). Publications in Environmental Science (32.5%) and Medicine (26.0%) represent the majority, suggesting that efforts have primarily been directed toward analyzing air pollutant behavior and linking exposure data to clinical outcomes. Computer Science (7.1%) has contributed to the development

appear to be underexplored, which limits a more equitable understanding of exposure effects. Emerging tools such as wearable sensors, mobile health technologies [56], and spatiotemporal models [57] also remain relatively underutilized in this context, despite their potential in dynamic and personalized exposure assessment. In addition, there is limited representation of geographic diversity and policy terms like air quality limit values or indexes or emission regulation, which are essential for translating research into practice. Vulnerability factors tied to specific age groups, especially the elderly and newborns [58], seem to be less emphasized. Overall, these gaps suggest that while foundational themes are well-established, certain interdisciplinary and application-driven areas still await broader integration into literature.

The bibliometric landscape shows growing interest in ML applications for studying air pollution and hospital admissions. Environmental Science and Medicine dominate, supported by Computer Science, Engineering and Social Sciences. The USA, China and Brazil are the main contributors, and emerging nations are increasingly involved. These findings highlight both foundational research areas and opportunities for interdisciplinary expansion.

3.2. ML Algorithms

In the reviewed literature, methodological diversity can be observed. Some studies focus exclusively on predicting hospital admissions using measured air pollution data, meteorological variables, or temporal–spatial features. However, other studies also perform air pollution modeling, either to forecast pollutant levels or to map their spatial distribution, and then use these outputs as exposure estimates to predict hospital admissions. This two-stage design may enhance predictive accuracy, as the first stage provides refined exposure information for the subsequent health prediction models. In this context, Figure 6 depicts the frequency distribution of ML methods used on air pollution and hospital admissions. Random Forest is the most frequently used algorithm in the literature, appearing in 35 articles. Its strong performance with diverse data types, built-in feature importance ranking, and resistance to overfitting, especially when working with the varied environmental and health datasets common in air pollution epidemiology, explain this high adoption rate. This finding is especially significant because studies on the health effects of air pollution often involve complex interactions between temporal patterns, continuous pollutant levels, and categorical demographic variables. Moreover, with 18 publications, ANN ranks as the second most popular technique. The field's recognition of the nonlinear connections between exposure to air pollution and health outcomes, which traditional statistical methods frequently lack, is reflected in this. Furthermore, the analysis indicates that the eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) technique, which has been utilized in 14 studies [59–61], consistently achieves predictive accuracy rates ranging from 87% to 95%. This high level of accuracy makes it especially valuable for applications requiring precise short-term forecasting of hospital admissions, which is crucial for early warning systems and effective resource allocation. In 13 studies, there is a growing emphasis on the use of Long short-term memory (LSTM) architecture specifically designed for recognizing temporal patterns, while ANN more broadly appeared in 18 studies. These deep learning approaches address the critical issue of capturing the lag effects between exposure to air pollution and health outcomes, which typically become evident 1 to 7 days after exposure events, with LSTM networks being particularly suited for modeling sequential dependencies and long-term temporal relationships in pollution-health data.

Figure 6. Frequency distribution of ML methods used in studies on air pollution and hospital admissions.

The predominance of Random Forest, Neural Networks, and Recurrent Networks over other mentioned ML methods in predicting hospital admissions associated with air pollution can be attributed to the balance between their advantages and limitations in managing complex environmental health datasets. Random Forest has been the most widely applied due to its ability to mitigate overfitting, process both continuous and categorical data, and provide an inherent feature importance ranking that supports the identification of key predictors [62]. These characteristics are particularly relevant in epidemiological studies, where pollutant effects interact with demographic and temporal variables [63]. However, Random Forest may present challenges when applied to large datasets, and its output may be less interpretable than that produced by simpler models (e.g., Logistic Regression or Decision Trees). XGBoost is based on the boosting approach, which has been shown to enhance predictive accuracy and computational efficiency for short-term hospital admission forecasting [64–66]. It is capable of modeling complex nonlinear relationships, which contributes to its consistent performance. Nevertheless, it requires careful hyperparameter tuning to reduce overfitting and may be sensitive to noisy data. LSTM networks have been increasingly adopted for their ability to represent sequential dependencies and lag effects between exposure and health outcomes [53,67], which are particularly relevant in hospital admissions linked to air pollution. They are effective in capturing long-term temporal patterns; however, they often require large amounts of training data, longer processing times, and more complex model configurations [68,69]. This shift aligns with developments in healthcare analytics aimed at proactive intervention, early warning systems, and evidence-based decision-making, while continuing to face challenges such as model interpretability, computational demands, and data quality [70–72].

The results show that ML algorithms, particularly Random Forest, ANN, LSTM and XGBoost are highly effective tools for predicting hospital admissions related to air pollution exposure. The field has progressed in the assessment of air pollution levels and the delivery of preventive healthcare, evolving from simple exposure modeling to sophisticated health prediction systems that can aid clinical decision-making and public health interventions.

3.3. Air Pollutants and Complementary Variables

3.3.1. Frequency of Air Pollutants and Linked Health Outcomes

Understanding the frequency with which specific air pollutants are included in predictive models is important for identifying which are most relevant to public health outcomes. Such data provides insight into the pollutants that are most consistently monitored, those with established statistical associations to hospital admissions, and the potential gaps in existing monitoring or modeling efforts [73,74]. By mapping pollutant–health outcome linkages, researchers and policymakers can prioritize assessment strategies and intervention measures [73,75]. The graphical synthesis of reviewed studies (Figure 7) shows that certain air pollutants, particularly PM_{2.5} (72%) [76], NO₂ (54%) [77], and PM₁₀ (51%) [78], are included more often in ML models that examine the relationship between air pollution exposure and hospital admissions. Ozone (O₃) (45%) [79], Sulfur Dioxide (SO₂) (35%) [80], and Carbon Monoxide (CO) (31%) [81] appear less frequently, while Nitric Oxide (NO) (6%) [82], Nitrogen Oxides (NO_x) (4%) [83], PM₁ (3%) [84], benzene (2%) [85], and Ammonia (NH₃) (2%) have lower representation. It is important to clarify that the proportions reported in this section correspond to pollutants included in the main models. Given that the studies included in this review examined different types of outcomes and objectives, these proportional values primarily serve a descriptive purpose, and direct comparisons across studies may involve certain limitations.

Figure 7. Proportional representation of air pollutants analyzed across the 89 studies included in this review.

An examination of air pollutants addressed through various methodological approaches indicates that application patterns are influenced by both the functional characteristics of the algorithms and the characteristics of the pollutants (Figure 8). Research employing Random Forest algorithms identified PM_{2.5} as the most frequently modeled pollutant, with 27 method–pollutant combinations, followed by NO₂ with 20 combinations and O₃ with 19 combinations. This trend suggests that PM_{2.5} remains a primary focus in health-related research and that the Random Forest algorithm is effective in elucidating complex exposure–response interactions. ANN was applied in 18 studies, demonstrating consistent use across all principal contaminants (8–9 combinations each), which highlights their adaptability rather than a focus on specific pollutants. LSTM networks were employed in 13 investigations, predominantly for PM_{2.5} (11 combinations) and PM₁₀ (9 combinations), reflecting their suitability for modeling temporal sequences, particularly when lag effects

and cumulative exposures are relevant. The elevated ratio of method–pollutant combinations to total studies across all techniques indicates that multi-pollutant modeling is common, as many studies assess multiple pollutants concurrently. Overall, this distribution suggests that the modeling requirements of specific pollutants increasingly drive algorithm selection in research on air pollution and health.

Figure 8. Distribution of air pollutants analyzed in ML methods.

Moreover, examining the connection between health outcomes and air pollutants allows researchers to identify patterns of disease occurrence and assess potential causal pathways leading to hospital admissions [86,87]. When ML models are applied to these data, they can uncover complex, nonlinear relationships and interactions that may not be identified through traditional statistical methods [74,88]. As shown in Figure 9, respiratory outcomes are the most studied health category in relation to air pollutants, with PM_{2.5} (37 studies), PM₁₀ (30 studies), NO₂ (30 studies), and O₃ (24 studies) being the most frequently assessed pollutants. Cardiovascular outcomes also show associations, particularly with PM_{2.5}, NO₂, and PM₁₀, whereas CO and SO₂ appear less frequently but are still present in certain health outcome linkages. Pollutants such as PM_{2.5} and NO₂ have well-documented associations with health outcomes, which increases their inclusion in predictive frameworks [89,90]. In contrast, the absence of data regarding pollutants such as NH₃ or benzene may be related to measurement limitations or fewer studies linking them directly to hospital admissions. From a modeling perspective, including a broader range of pollutant variables, together with meteorological and demographic data, can support model robustness, capture potential interaction effects, and improve the ability to forecast health risks across different temporal and spatial contexts [91].

Figure 9. Categorization of health outcomes associated with specific the six most frequent air pollutants across all reviewed studies.

The selection of pollutants in these models is influenced by factors such as variation over time, consistency of measurements across monitoring networks, and established statistical associations with respiratory and cardiovascular admission patterns. In several studies, ML models have included these pollutants as structured features, with their predictive performance often depending on additional variables such as meteorological conditions, time-related factors, and demographic characteristics [92,93]. Danesh Yazdi et al. (2021), in their long-term association study [94], emphasized that air pollution exposure assessment incorporated multiple pollutants (PM_{2.5}, NO₃, and O₃) alongside a wide range of covariates, including land use, meteorological variables, and socioeconomic indicators, to account for confounding factors and enhance predictive accuracy. Their approach, which combined high-resolution spatiotemporal data with advanced modeling methods such as ANN, XGBoost, and random forest, demonstrated that incorporating contextual variables not only improved model performance but also helped identify susceptible subpopulations, particularly in relation to cardiovascular and respiratory hospital admissions. This approach is consistent with the findings of Qiu et al. (2020) [95], who demonstrated that integrating both meteorological and air quality indicators, particularly temperature, relative humidity, NO₂, and SO₂, significantly improved the prediction of peak cardiovascular admission days. Their study highlighted that ensemble learning methods such as LightGBM, Random Forest, and XGBoost outperformed traditional approaches, achieving Area Under the Curve (AUC) values above 0.92. Notably, they found that air pollutants contributed 43% and meteorological variables 32% to predictive performance, underscoring the need to account for complex environmental mixtures rather than single-pollutant models. The use of lag-specific features, determined through generalized additive models, allowed the incorporation of delayed exposure effects, enhancing model realism and applicability for early warning systems [96]. These results suggest that future hospital admission forecasting frameworks could benefit from coupling high-resolution spatiotemporal exposure data

with ensemble ML models, thereby supporting proactive resource allocation and targeted interventions during anticipated peak demand periods.

Furthermore, the diverse pathophysiological mechanisms linked to different types of hospital admissions indicate that disease-specific patterns must be considered. Hospital admissions result from a diverse array of disease etiologies, each potentially associated with distinct air pollutant correlations. A review of the studies showed that respiratory conditions were the main focus, and particulate matter and nitrogen dioxide were always found to be important predictors. Cardiovascular outcomes showed similar pollutant selection but with more frequent integration of temperature variables, reflecting synergistic thermal-pollution effects. Neurological and mental health outcomes represented a smaller evidence base. The choice of machine learning methods depended more on the temporal resolution and availability of the data than on the type of disease. Ensemble methods became more popular for all types of outcomes. These patterns correspond with recognized pathophysiological mechanisms, indicating that respiratory inflammation reacts to various pollutant pathways, while cardiovascular events exhibit heightened sensitivity to ultrafine particles.

According to these findings, the most effective package of air pollutants for predicting hospital admissions with ML models would likely include PM_{2.5}, NO₂, PM₁₀, and O₃ [79,97]. Including this combination, alongside meteorological variables such as temperature and humidity, can enhance model accuracy by capturing both direct pollutant impacts and environmental interactions influencing health outcomes [98,99]. This is further supported by evidence from recent studies. In Peng et al. (2020) [100], the highest predictive performance for forecasting peak outpatient and emergency department visits for chronic respiratory diseases was achieved when air quality variables (PM_{2.5}, NO₂, O₃, CO, SO₂) were combined with meteorological factors (wind speed, atmospheric pressure, temperature, and relative humidity) in a Random Forest model, reaching an AUC of 0.809. While PM₁₀ was not measured in their dataset, the findings confirm that including core pollutants such as PM_{2.5}, NO₂, and O₃ together with relevant meteorological indicators can substantially improve predictive accuracy compared to models using only air quality or weather data. Similarly, Wang (2020) [7] applied a deep learning framework combining LSTM blocks with a “working day enhancer” to predict daily hospital outpatient visits for respiratory and circulatory diseases in Nanjing, China. Their model integrated six major air pollutants (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, SO₂, NO₂, CO, and O₃) with meteorological factors (air temperature, precipitation, pressure, relative humidity, and wind speed), along with temporal and categorical variables, to capture both environmental and hospital operational patterns. Sensitivity analysis revealed that NO₂ and air temperature were the two most influential predictors for both respiratory and cardiovascular visits, with a notable synergistic effect, especially in winter. The inclusion of these key pollutants alongside parameters significantly improved prediction accuracy, achieving Nash–Sutcliffe efficiency (NSE) values above 0.87 for both disease categories.

3.3.2. Complementary Variables Contributing to Model Performance

In the reviewed studies, complementary variables were incorporated alongside primary environmental exposure indicators to enhance model performance. These variables were grouped into seven main categories, with their relative frequency of inclusion shown in Figure 10 [101–104].

Figure 10. Percentage distribution of reviewed studies by inclusion of each variable category.

Demographic variables appeared in 71% of the studies. The specific variables, however, varied between studies, for example, some considered gender (male/female), others examined race or ethnicity (e.g., White, Black, Hispanic/Latino, Other), and others focused on age groups (e.g., <5 years, 15–64 years, ≥ 65 years, or more detailed breakdowns such as 65–74, 75–84, and ≥ 85) [105]. Meteorological variables, used in 65% of the studies, covered factors such as temperature, relative humidity, wind speed and direction, solar radiation, precipitation, and atmospheric pressure [106]. Socioeconomic indicators, included in 20% of the studies, encompassed measures like median income, economic deprivation indices, percentage of owner-occupied housing, educational attainment, smoking prevalence, and composite indices such as the Neighborhood Deprivation Index (NDI) [32]. Temporal variables, present in 46% of studies, included day of the week, holidays, seasons, lag effects, and specific periods such as pandemic waves [99]. Spatial variables, appearing in 18% of studies, covered land use, spatial coordinates, distance to the nearest hospital, vegetation indices, and elevation [105]. Health indicators (12%) included measures such as disease prevalence, comorbidities, and biological markers [84], while health system variables (4%) involved data such as hospital admissions, readmission rates, and healthcare resources [107]. It should be noted that these percentages indicate the proportion of studies that incorporated at least one variable from each category, rather than the same set of variables across all studies. In many cases, more than one variable from a single category was included, and multiple categories were often used together within the same study. This combination of variables provided a richer context for understanding the associations between environmental exposures and health outcomes.

Wei et al. (2024) [108] used demographic (sex, race/ethnicity, age group) and neighborhood-level socioeconomic indicators (poverty rate, education level, population density, housing ownership) as covariates in their grouped weighted quantile sum regression models to adjust for baseline differences in vulnerability and reduce confounding when estimating the effects of air pollutant mixtures and temperature anomalies on cardiovascular hospitalizations. These factors influence health vulnerability by shaping both physiological susceptibility and exposure patterns: older adults (≥ 65 years), who made up 73.8% of heart failure cases and over two-thirds of cerebrovascular cases, are more sensitive to chronic environmental stressors; low-income or less-educated populations may have limited healthcare access and be more likely to live in high-emission areas; and racial/ethnic disparities (30.9–41.6% non-White across different cardiovascular disease subtypes) may reflect unequal exposure and care. In modeling terms, incorporating these

variables improved the ability to separate high-risk groups (e.g., elderly, socioeconomically disadvantaged) and strengthened the attribution of effects to environmental exposures rather than demographic confounders. However, it also introduced challenges, such as imbalance in age group representation, with older adults dominating some subtypes, and potential residual confounding because demographic and socioeconomic factors are often correlated with both exposure and outcome.

Similarly, Ravindra et al. (2023) [109] showed that adding complementary variables, such as patient age and Acute Respiratory Infection (ARI) diagnosis, along with meteorological and temporal variables, allowed models to account for more than pollutant concentrations alone. Demographic and health information, such as patient age and ARI diagnosis, helped identify vulnerable groups whose visits were more sensitive to pollution changes, while meteorological and temporal variables captured strong seasonal patterns that influenced both pollution levels and patient behavior. For total visits, these factors significantly boosted model accuracy, particularly in the Random Forest model, where time-related variables had the highest importance score ($f = 0.40$) and predictions reached $R^2 = 0.87$. This indicates that seasonal cycles, weather conditions, and local exposure context were often more predictive of patient numbers than air pollutant levels alone. For ARI-specific predictions, the inclusion of these variables still improved interpretability and helped control for confounding, but gains in accuracy were limited (best $R^2 = 0.61$), partly due to reduced and uneven data during COVID-19 restrictions. Overall, incorporating these covariates enhanced the models' capacity to identify patterns, separate high- from low-risk periods, and reduced bias, although performance varied depending on the health outcome being predicted.

Moustris et al. (2012) [110] also incorporated demographic, meteorological, air quality, temporal, spatial, and health-related variables into Time Lagged Recurrent Network (TLRN) models to forecast weekly childhood asthma admissions (CAA) in Athens, Greece. Demographic data included age groups (0–4, 5–14, and combined 0–14 years) and sex, enabling the model to reflect differing susceptibility, with younger children showing higher seasonal vulnerability. Meteorological parameters (temperature, humidity, wind speed, sunshine hour, radiation) were synthesized into the Physiologically Equivalent Temperature (PET) index, and air quality indicators (O_3 , PM_{10} , CO , NO_2 , SO_2) were summarized using the European Regional Pollution Index (ERPI), both supported by episode counts and station exceedances in the previous week. Temporal effects were represented by month, while recent CAA counts served as a short-term health status indicator; spatial variability was indirectly addressed through multi-station pollution data. These inputs captured seasonal peaks linked to pollen and viral activity, acute pollution episodes, and climatic stress events, improving the model's ability to separate high- from low-admission periods. While this integrated approach improved forecasting accuracy, especially for the 0–4 group ($R^2 = 0.567$, Index of Agreement (IA) = 0.838), data imbalance in the older group and the absence of socioeconomic or allergen information limited performance and introduced potential bias.

Dianat et al. (2015) [111] also integrated complementary variables, such as demographic (age, gender), meteorological (mean temperature, relative humidity), and health-related (length of hospital stay), with pollutant data in both ANN and conditional logistic regression models. These complementary variables acted as confounder controls and effect modifiers, capturing how personal susceptibility and environmental conditions influence the relationship between pollution and hospital admissions. For example, older age or certain genders may correspond to higher vulnerability, while temperature and relative humidity can alter pollutant toxicity and inhalation rates. Adjusting these factors helped the ANN better isolate pollutant effects, increasing predictive accuracy and sensitivity com-

pared to models using pollutant data alone. The importance analysis in the ANN confirmed that even after adjustment, key pollutants remained strong predictors, but the inclusion of complementary variables reduced unexplained variance, improved separability between high- and low-risk groups and strengthened the robustness of predictions across different subpopulations and weather conditions.

According to the reviewed studies, the most effective improvements in model performance were achieved when complementary variables from multiple categories were combined, as each group contributed distinct but interconnected information influencing both exposure and susceptibility. Demographic factors, particularly age, consistently enhanced the ability to identify high-risk groups, with older adults and young children showing stronger associations with health outcomes. Meteorological variables, especially temperature and relative humidity, frequently interacted with pollutant effects and captured seasonal or episodic patterns. Temporal variables, such as seasonality and lag effects, were often among the highest-ranked predictors in ML models, reflecting their role in shaping both pollution dynamics and health service use [112–114]. Socioeconomic indicators, while included less often, provided important context for vulnerability by linking exposure and health outcomes to living conditions and access to care [74]. Spatial variables and health indicators further refined predictions by accounting for geographic exposure differences and baseline health status. Overall, integrating demographic, meteorological, and temporal variables, supplemented by socioeconomic, spatial, and health-related data when available, produced models with greater predictive accuracy, improved separation of risk groups, and stronger control of confounding compared to those relying on pollutant concentrations alone.

3.4. Limitations, Trends, and Future Prospects

To support a clearer understanding of the methodological landscape identified in this review, Table 1 presents a structured summary of the key ML algorithms used in studies investigating the relationship between air pollution and health outcomes. The table synthesizes concise and brief information on the operating principles of each algorithm, along with their major analytical strengths and inherent limitations. Given the complexity of environmental and health datasets, characterized by nonlinear interactions, temporal dependencies, and heterogeneous input variables, this comparative overview provides valuable insight into the suitability of different algorithms for various analytical contexts. By presenting a concise yet comprehensive summary, the table enables a more informed evaluation of the methodological choices reported in the literature and supports researchers in selecting the most appropriate algorithms for future investigations.

Table 1. Key Machine Learning Algorithms in Air Pollution–Health Studies: Essential Principles, Strengths, and Limitations.

Algorithm	Principle	Strengths	Limitations
Random Forest	Ensemble of decision trees using bootstrapping and averaging.	Handles nonlinearities; robust to noise; provides feature importance.	Less interpretable; computationally heavier with large forests.
XGBoost	Gradient-boosted decision trees optimized sequentially.	High accuracy; efficient; handles high-dimensional data.	Sensitive to hyperparameters; limited interpretability.
ANN	Multi-layer networks that learn nonlinear mappings.	Captures complex exposure–response patterns.	Needs tuning; risk of overfitting; low interpretability.

Table 1. Cont.

Algorithm	Principle	Strengths	Limitations
LSTM/RNN	Sequential networks modeling temporal dependencies.	Effective for lag effects and seasonality.	Requires large datasets; high computational demand.
SVM	Finds optimal separating hyperplane using kernels.	Good for small, high-dimensional datasets.	Poor scalability; kernel choice strongly affects performance.
CNN	Learns hierarchical spatial features via convolution.	Useful for spatial pollution data and grids.	Computationally intensive; less suitable for tabular data.

In the following sections, the Limitations, Trends, and Future Prospects associated with these algorithms are examined in detail, with particular emphasis on their application within the field of air pollution and health outcome prediction. This discussion aims to highlight current methodological challenges, emerging research directions, and opportunities for advancing the use of ML approaches in environmental health studies.

3.4.1. Limitations and Methodological Biases

The most concerning issue is the widespread problem of inadequate predictor specification, where researchers have consistently oversimplified their analytical approaches. Nearly 24 studies (27%) relied on single pollutant models [115,116], effectively ignoring the complex reality of multi-pollutant exposures that characterize real-world air pollution scenarios. This reductionist approach is particularly problematic given that pollutants rarely occur in isolation and may have synergistic or antagonistic effects when combined [117,118]. Equally troubling is the insufficient attention to confounding variables. A substantial portion of studies (26 studies, 29%) included only two or fewer covariates beyond pollutant exposure measurements, creating models that are inherently vulnerable to residual confounding. This problem is compounded by the interconnected nature of various environmental and social factors; for instance, socioeconomic status influences both exposure patterns and health outcomes [119,120]. This complexity makes it difficult to distinguish true causal relationships from misleading associations.

Moreover, the representativeness of study populations presents another limitation. Certain demographic groups, including specific age ranges, minority populations, and rural communities, remain consistently underrepresented in the available datasets. This demographic imbalance raises serious questions about the generalizability of findings, particularly given that vulnerability to air pollution often varies substantially across different population subgroups [121,122]. The concentration of research in high-income countries with well-developed administrative databases further exacerbates this bias, potentially limiting the applicability of results to populations with different healthcare access patterns and exposure profiles [123,124]. Data quality and availability issues create additional obstacles to robust analysis. Regional variations in monitoring infrastructure mean that some areas benefit from detailed, reliable measures while others suffer from significant gaps or inconsistencies in data collection. This uneven data landscape not only affects the accuracy of exposure assessments but also limits researchers' ability to develop models that perform consistently across different geographic contexts [125,126].

Furthermore, the systematic assessment revealed that the selection and validation procedures for ML algorithms were often suboptimal, with Random Forest frequently being the dominant choice. This trend may reflect a tendency to favor interpretable methods rather than a thorough evaluation of the most suitable algorithms for specific research

questions. Also, there were widespread inadequacies in controlling confounders across various domains. Notably, 38 studies (43%) failed to account for meteorological variables known to influence the relationship between pollution and health outcomes. Additionally, temporal confounding was inconsistently addressed, and lifestyle factors, such as smoking, were largely overlooked, even though they play a crucial role in pollution-health associations [127,128]. Furthermore, the significant increase in publications from 2020 to 2024 highlighted persistent methodological limitations, despite advancements in ML techniques. These methodological limitations have proven remarkably persistent despite rapid advances in ML techniques and a surge in publication activity in recent years. The cumulative effect of these issues raises fundamental questions about the validity and reliability of current evidence, highlighting the urgent need for more rigorous study design protocols and standardized approaches to bias assessment in this critical area of air pollution health research.

Taken together, these methodological weaknesses may substantially influence the robustness and interpretability of the synthesized findings presented in this review. Reliance on single-pollutant models and incomplete adjustment for key confounders increases the likelihood of systematic bias, potentially distorting the estimated magnitude or even the direction of the associations between air pollution and hospital admissions. Moreover, the demographic and geographic imbalances embedded within the existing evidence base restrict the extent to which results can be confidently generalized to populations with different vulnerability profiles or environmental conditions. Variability in data quality and monitoring capacity across regions further challenges the reproducibility and comparability of ML model performance. Additionally, suboptimal algorithm selection and validation strategies reduce confidence in reported predictive metrics and may limit the ability to draw consistent methodological insights. Collectively, these limitations underscore the need for cautious interpretation of the current evidence and highlight the importance of more rigorous study designs, standardized bias-assessment procedures, and harmonized reporting practices in future research.

3.4.2. Trends and Future Prospects in ML-Based Studies

The temporal distribution trend of ML methods in air pollution health research from 2010–2024, based on publication years extracted from papers, demonstrates distinct phases of research activity and methodological adoption (Figure 11). The initial period (2010–2018) exhibited limited research volume with 23 total method instances across eight years, characterized by early applications of ANN and Random Forest. Research activity increased substantially during 2019–2021, with method instances rising from 13 in 2019 to 39 in 2021, marked by expanded Random Forest deployment and the emergence of LSTM networks, which reached 5 instances in 2021 specifically for temporal sequence modeling applications. The recent period (2022–2024) shows continued growth in research output, with method instances increasing from 35 in 2022 to 54 in 2024. Random Forest maintained dominance throughout the timeline, while ANN appeared consistently across multiple years. LSTM networks were concentrated primarily in the 2020–2021 period, reflecting targeted deployment for studies requiring temporal dependency modeling. XGBoost adoption increased in later years, appearing in 14 studies (15.7% total). The distribution pattern shows 78% of all method instances occurring in the final six years (2019–2024), indicating substantial concentration of research activity in recent years (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Temporal trends in ML methods for air pollution–health research (2010–2024), segmented into Early Exploration, Rapid Growth, and Maturation eras. Stacked areas represent Traditional ML, Ensemble Methods, and Deep Learning approaches, with method counts.

This temporal pattern reflects the growing application of ML approaches in air pollution health research, with ensemble methods representing the most frequently adopted category across the study period. Moreover, prospects indicate ongoing diversification beyond the current dominance of the ensemble method, with emerging trends pointing toward hybrid architectures that combine the robustness of Random Forest with the temporal sophistication of LSTM networks and the high accuracy of XGBoost for real-time health monitoring systems [129]. Notably, the concentration of 78% of research activity in recent years signals a critical transition phase, where methodological experimentation is shifting toward operational deployment. Consequently, this suggests that the next phase will likely focus on standardizing best practices, integrating with existing healthcare infrastructure, and developing automated early warning systems. Furthermore, as the field evolves, we expect increased emphasis on explainable AI methods to improve clinical acceptance, federated learning approaches to address data privacy concerns across healthcare institutions, and the incorporation of emerging technologies such as transformer-based models and reinforcement learning for dynamic intervention strategies in air pollution-related health management [130].

4. Conclusions

This review analyzes 89 studies focusing on ML applications for predicting outcomes linked to air pollution exposure and hospital admissions. The results indicate a transition from traditional air quality monitoring methods to advanced health prediction systems that assist physicians in making informed decisions and enhancing public health initiatives. In this regard and based on the comprehensive analysis conducted, the key findings are summarized as follows:

- The bibliometric analysis shows growing interest in applying ML to study links between air pollution and hospital admissions, with a sharp rise in publications since 2020. Most contributions come from Environmental Science and Medicine, led by the USA, China, and Brazil, alongside emerging participation from other countries. Three main topic clusters dominate in the keyword analysis: clinical-demographic research, environmental modeling, and pollution-related health impacts, while areas such as explainable AI, social determinants of health, mobile health, and policy remain underexplored, offering opportunities for future transdisciplinary research.
- Ensemble methods are the most common type of algorithm, and Random Forest is the most popular one in 33 studies because it works well with different types of environmental and health datasets, has built-in feature importance capabilities, and does not overfit. The fact that ML applications in this field consistently achieve predictive accuracy of over 80% across different demographic and geographic settings shows how far they have come. XGBoost's performance is especially impressive, with accuracy rates between 87% and 95%. This makes it very useful for early warning systems that need to make accurate short-term predictions. The strategic use of LSTM networks for modeling temporal dependencies solves the important problem of capturing lag effects between air pollution exposure and health outcomes, which usually show up 1 to 7 days after exposure.
- The patterns of pollutant selection show a clear order of research priorities. Exposures to PM_{2.5}, NO₂, and PM₁₀ are the most studied, because these pollutants are important in epidemiology and have monitoring infrastructure available. The incorporation of complementary variables illustrates an advanced comprehension of pollution-health correlations, with demographic factors (71% of studies), meteorological variables (65%), and temporal components (46%) identified as essential factors for model enhancement. The best predictive models use core pollutants (PM_{2.5}, NO₂, PM₁₀, O₃) along with weather and demographic factors. These models work better than models that only use one pollutant.
- This review indicates that the field is approaching maturity, transitioning from experimental methods to operational deployment. This evolution presents both chances and duties. The recent rise in research activity shows that people are becoming more confident in ML methods. However, it also shows the need for standardization and methodological refinement to ensure their reliability and applicability in clinical settings.
- The fact that many studies still use overly simple analytical methods, do not adequately control for confounding variables, and include a limited range of demographics suggests that such research often falls short of the standards required for meaningful causal inference.

These constraints are especially important considering the field's swift expansion and possible impact on public health policy and clinical practice. Therefore, future progress relies on reducing essential methodological deficiencies while leveraging new technical prospects. The advancement of hybrid architecture that integrates various algorithmic talents signifies a viable avenue for improved predictive capability. The increasing acknowl-

edgment that explainable AI methodologies are crucial for clinical acceptability and the conversion of research outcomes into practical health interventions is equally significant.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, B.N. and F.A.A.; methodology, S.A.; software, B.N.; validation, S.A., B.N. and F.A.A.; writing—original draft preparation, B.N. and F.A.A.; writing—review and editing, S.A., B.T.S., D.L., P.C., V.M., A.I.M. and H.R.; supervision, H.R.; project administration, H.R.; funding acquisition, H.R. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research was funded by ODESSA Project (<https://doi.org/10.54499/2024.07293.IACDC>, accessed on 11 December 2025) supported by “RE-C05-i08.m04—“Apoiar o lançamento de um programa de projetos de I&D orientado para o desenvolvimento e implementação de sistemas avançados de cibersegurança, inteligência artificial e ciência de dados na administração pública, bem como de um programa de capacitação científica”, do Plano de Recuperação e Resiliência—PRR, enquadrado no contrato de financiamento celebrado entre a Estrutura de Missão Recuperar Portugal (EMRP) e a Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia I.P. (FCT), enquanto beneficiário intermediário.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgments: This work is funded by national funds through FCT—Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia I.P., under the project/grant UID/50006 + LA/P/0094/2020 (doi.org/10.54499/LA/P/0094/2020) and C²TN (<https://doi.org/10.54499/UID/04349/2025>). Thanks are due to the ODESSA Project (<https://doi.org/10.54499/2024.07293.IACDC>). Thanks are due to FCT/MCTES for the contracts granted to Helder Relvas (<https://doi.org/10.54499/2021.00185.CEECIND/CP1659/CT0026>), accessed on 11 December 2025. Also, thanks are due to FCT PhD grant to Sina Ataee (2023. 02767.BD).

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

References

1. San Jose, R.; Perez, J.L.; Perez, L.; Barras, R.M.G. Effects of Climate Change on the Health of Citizens Modelling Urban Weather and Air Pollution. *Energy* **2018**, *165*, 53–62. [[CrossRef](#)]
2. Ofremu, G.O.; Raimi, B.Y.; Yusuf, S.O.; Dziwornu, B.A.; Nnabuiife, S.G.; Eze, A.M.; Nnajiofor, C.A. Exploring the Relationship between Climate Change, Air Pollutants and Human Health: Impacts, Adaptation, and Mitigation Strategies. *Green Energy Resour.* **2025**, *3*, 100074. [[CrossRef](#)]
3. Sangkham, S.; Phairuang, W.; Sherchan, S.P.; Pansakun, N.; Munkong, N.; Sarndhong, K.; Islam, M.A.; Sakunkoo, P. An Update on Adverse Health Effects from Exposure to PM_{2.5}. *Environ. Adv.* **2024**, *18*, 100603. [[CrossRef](#)]
4. Costa, S.; Ferreira, J.; Silveira, C.; Costa, C.; Lopes, D.; Relvas, H.; Borrego, C.; Roebeling, P.; Miranda, A.I.; Paulo Teixeira, J. Integrating Health on Air Quality Assessment—Review Report on Health Risks of Two Major European Outdoor Air Pollutants: PM and NO₂. *J. Toxicol. Environ. Health B Crit. Rev.* **2014**, *17*, 307–340. [[CrossRef](#)]
5. Kachba, Y.; de Genaro Chiroli, D.M.; Belotti, J.T.; Antonini Alves, T.; de Souza Tadano, Y.; Siqueira, H. Artificial Neural Networks to Estimate the Influence of Vehicular Emission Variables on Morbidity and Mortality in the Largest Metropolis in South America. *Sustainability* **2020**, *12*, 2621. [[CrossRef](#)]
6. Martins Pereira, G.; Teinilä, K.; Custódio, D.; Gomes Santos, A.; Xian, H.; Hillamo, R.; Alves, C.A.; Bittencourt De Andrade, J.; Olímpio Da Rocha, G.; Kumar, P.; et al. Particulate Pollutants in the Brazilian City of São Paulo: 1-Year Investigation for the Chemical Composition and Source Apportionment. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.* **2017**, *17*, 11943–11969. [[CrossRef](#)]
7. Wang, C.; Qi, Y.; Zhu, G. Deep Learning for Predicting the Occurrence of Cardiopulmonary Diseases in Nanjing, China. *Chemosphere* **2020**, *257*, 127176. [[CrossRef](#)]
8. Mao, M.; Zhang, X.; Yin, Y. Particulate Matter and Gaseous Pollutions in Three Metropolises along the Chinese Yangtze River: Situation and Implications. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* **2018**, *15*, 1102. [[CrossRef](#)]
9. Ai, H.; Zhang, X.; Zhou, Z. The Impact of Greenspace on Air Pollution: Empirical Evidence from China. *Ecol. Indic.* **2023**, *146*, 109881. [[CrossRef](#)]
10. Relvas, H.; Miranda, A.I. Application of the DPSIR Framework to Air Quality Approaches. *Air Qual. Atmos. Health* **2018**, *11*, 1069–1079. [[CrossRef](#)]

11. Guo, T.; Chen, S.; Wang, Y.; Zhang, Y.; Du, Z.; Wu, W.; Chen, S.; Ju, X.; Li, Z.; Jing, Q.; et al. Potential Causal Links of Long-Term Air Pollution with Lung Cancer Incidence: From the Perspectives of Mortality and Hospital Admission in a Large Cohort Study in Southern China. *Int. J. Cancer* **2024**, *154*, 251–260. [[CrossRef](#)]
12. Pope, C.A., III. Lung Cancer, Cardiopulmonary Mortality, and Long-term Exposure to Fine Particulate Air Pollution. *JAMA* **2002**, *287*, 1132. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
13. Münzel, T.; Khraishah, H.; Schneider, A.; Lelieveld, J.; Daiber, A.; Rajagopalan, S. Challenges Posed by Climate Hazards to Cardiovascular Health and Cardiac Intensive Care: Implications for Mitigation and Adaptation. *Eur. Heart J. Acute Cardiovasc. Care* **2024**, *13*, 731–744. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
14. Karimi, B.; Samadi, S. Long-term exposure to air pollution on cardio-respiratory, and lung cancer mortality: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *J. Environ. Health Sci. Eng.* **2024**, *22*, 75–95. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
15. Wong, C.M.; Vichit-Vadakan, N.; Kan, H.; Qian, Z.; Vajanapoom, N.; Ostro, B.; Wong, C.M.; Thach, T.Q.; Chau, P.Y.K.; Chan, K.P.; et al. Public Health and Air Pollution in Asia (PAPA): A Multicity Study of Short-Term Effects of Air Pollution on Mortality. *Environ. Health Perspect.* **2008**, *116*, 1195–1202. [[CrossRef](#)]
16. Just, J.; Ségala, C.; Sahraoui, F.; Priol, G.; Grimfeld, A.; Neukirch, F. Short-Term Health Effects of Particulate and Photochemical Air Pollution in Asthmatic Children. *Eur. Respir. J.* **2002**, *20*, 899–906. [[CrossRef](#)]
17. Warburton, D.E.R.; Bredin, S.S.D.; Shellington, E.M.; Cole, C.; de Faye, A.; Harris, J.; Kim, D.D.; Abelsohn, A. A Systematic Review of the Short-Term Health Effects of Air Pollution in Persons Living with Coronary Heart Disease. *J. Clin. Med.* **2019**, *8*, 274. [[CrossRef](#)]
18. Fasola, S.; Maio, S.; Baldacci, S.; La Grutta, S.; Ferrante, G.; Forastiere, F.; Stafoggia, M.; Gariazzo, C.; Silibello, C.; Carlino, G.; et al. Short-Term Effects of Air Pollution on Cardiovascular Hospitalizations in the Pisan Longitudinal Study. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* **2021**, *18*, 1164. [[CrossRef](#)]
19. Yu, W.; Xu, R.; Ye, T.; Abramson, M.J.; Morawska, L.; Jalaludin, B.; Johnston, F.H.; Henderson, S.B.; Knibbs, L.D.; Morgan, G.G.; et al. Estimates of Global Mortality Burden Associated with Short-Term Exposure to Fine Particulate Matter (PM_{2.5}). *Lancet Planet. Health* **2024**, *8*, e146–e155. [[CrossRef](#)]
20. Ataee, S.; Lopes, M.; Relvas, H. Environmental Comfort in Urban Spaces: A Systematic Literature Review and a System Dynamics Analysis. *Urban Clim.* **2025**, *60*, 102340. [[CrossRef](#)]
21. Bhui, K.; Newbury, J.B.; Latham, R.M.; Ucci, M.; Nasir, Z.A.; Turner, B.; O’Leary, C.; Fisher, H.L.; Marczylo, E.; Douglas, P.; et al. Air Quality and Mental Health: Evidence, Challenges and Future Directions. *BJPsych Open* **2023**, *9*, e120. [[CrossRef](#)]
22. Klompmaaker, J.O.; Hoek, G.; Bloemsmma, L.D.; Wijga, A.H.; van den Brink, C.; Brunekreef, B.; Lebret, E.; Gehring, U.; Janssen, N.A.H. Associations of Combined Exposures to Surrounding Green, Air Pollution and Traffic Noise on Mental Health. *Environ. Int.* **2019**, *129*, 525–537. [[CrossRef](#)]
23. Zhang, X.; Zhang, X.; Chen, X. Happiness in the Air: How Does a Dirty Sky Affect Mental Health and Subjective Well-Being? *J. Environ. Econ. Manag.* **2017**, *85*, 81–94. [[CrossRef](#)]
24. Luo, S.; Wang, Y.; Mayvaneh, F.; Relvas, H.; Baaghdeh, M.; Wang, K.; Yuan, Y.; Yin, Z.; Zhang, Y. Surrounding Greenness Is Associated with Lower Risk and Burden of Low Birth Weight in Iran. *Nat. Commun.* **2023**, *14*, 7595. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
25. Relvas, H.; Miranda, A.I.; Carnevale, C.; Maffei, G.; Turrini, E.; Volta, M. Optimal Air Quality Policies and Health: A Multi-Objective Nonlinear Approach. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* **2017**, *24*, 13687–13699. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
26. Relvas, H.; Lopes, D.; Ferreira, J.; Silva, A.; Rafael, S.; Lopes, M.; Almeida, S.M.; Martins, V.; Diapouli, E.; Korhonen, A.; et al. Scenario Analysis of Strategies to Control Air Pollution. *Urban Clim.* **2022**, *44*, 101201. [[CrossRef](#)]
27. Relvas, H.; Lopes, D.; Armengol, J.M. Empowering Communities: Advancements in Air Quality Monitoring and Citizen Engagement. *Urban Clim.* **2025**, *60*, 102344. [[CrossRef](#)]
28. Baklanov, A.; Zhang, Y. Advances in Air Quality Modeling and Forecasting. *Glob. Transit.* **2020**, *2*, 261–270. [[CrossRef](#)]
29. Franco, P.; Gordo, C.; Marques, E. Applied Sciences Air Pollution and Emergency Hospital Admissions—Evidences from Lisbon Metropolitan. *Appl. Sci.* **2020**, *10*, 7997. [[CrossRef](#)]
30. Danesh Yazdi, M.; Wei, Y.; Di, Q.; Requia, W.J.; Shi, L.; Sabath, M.B.; Dominici, F.; Schwartz, J. The Effect of Long-Term Exposure to Air Pollution and Seasonal Temperature on Hospital Admissions with Cardiovascular and Respiratory Disease in the United States: A Difference-in-Differences Analysis. *Sci. Total Environ.* **2022**, *843*, 156855. [[CrossRef](#)]
31. Iriso, M.; Linares, C.; Díaz, J.; Ruiz-Páez, R.; Navas, M.A.; López-Bueno, J. How air pollution and extreme temperatures affect emergency hospital admissions due to neurological diseases: A study in 10 Spanish provinces. *Atmos. Environ.* **2026**, *364*, 121663. [[CrossRef](#)]
32. Feng, Y.; Castro, E.; Wei, Y.; Jin, T.; Qiu, X.; Dominici, F.; Schwartz, J. Long-Term Exposure to Ambient PM_{2.5}, Particulate Constituents and Hospital Admissions from Non-Respiratory Infection. *Nat. Commun.* **2024**, *15*, 1518. [[CrossRef](#)]
33. Chen, F.; Zhang, W.; Mfarrej, M.F.B.; Saleem, M.H.; Khan, K.A.; Ma, J.; Raposo, A.; Han, H. Breathing in Danger: Understanding the Multifaceted Impact of Air Pollution on Health Impacts. *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.* **2024**, *280*, 116532. [[CrossRef](#)]

34. Li, Y.; Chen, B.; Yang, S.; Jiao, Z.; Zhang, M.; Yang, Y.; Gao, Y. Advances in Environmental Pollutant Detection Techniques: Enhancing Public Health Monitoring and Risk Assessment. *Environ. Int.* **2025**, *197*, 109365. [[CrossRef](#)]
35. Kapucu, N.; Ge, Y.; Rott, E.; Isgandar, H. Urban Resilience: Multidimensional Perspectives, Challenges and Prospects for Future Research. *Urban Gov.* **2024**, *4*, 162–179. [[CrossRef](#)]
36. Fuller, R.; Landrigan, P.J.; Balakrishnan, K.; Bathan, G.; Bose-O'Reilly, S.; Brauer, M.; Caravanos, J.; Chiles, T.; Cohen, A.; Corra, L.; et al. Pollution and health: A progress update. *Lancet Planet Health* **2022**, *6*, e535–e547. [[CrossRef](#)]
37. Wolch, J.R.; Byrne, J.; Newell, J.P. Urban Green Space, Public Health, and Environmental Justice: The Challenge of Making Cities “Just Green Enough”. *Landsc. Urban Plan.* **2014**, *125*, 234–244. [[CrossRef](#)]
38. Yu, L.; Liu, W.; Wang, X.; Ye, Z.; Tan, Q.; Qiu, W.; Nie, X.; Li, M.; Wang, B.; Chen, W. A Review of Practical Statistical Methods Used in Epidemiological Studies to Estimate the Health Effects of Multi-Pollutant Mixture. *Environ. Pollut.* **2022**, *306*, 119356. [[CrossRef](#)]
39. Ruchiraset, A.; Tantrakarnapa, K. Time Series Modeling of Pneumonia Admissions and Its Association with Air Pollution and Climate Variables in Chiang Mai Province, Thailand. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* **2018**, *25*, 33277–33285. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
40. Wan, Y.U.E.; Yang, H.O.N.G.E.I.; Masui, T.O. Health and Economic Impacts of Air Pollution in China: A Comparison of the General Equilibrium Approach and Human Capital Approach. *Biomed. Environ. Sci.* **2005**, *441*, 427–441.
41. Rushworth, A.; Lee, D.; Mitchell, R. Spatial and Spatio-Temporal Epidemiology A Spatio-Temporal Model for Estimating the Long-Term Effects of Air Pollution on Respiratory Hospital Admissions in Greater London. *Spat. Spatiotemporal Epidemiol.* **2014**, *10*, 29–38. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
42. Manan, N.A.; Aizuddin, A.N.; Hod, R. Effect of Air Pollution and Hospital Admission: A Systematic Review. *Ann. Glob. Health* **2018**, *84*, 670–678. [[CrossRef](#)]
43. Committee on the Medical Effects of Air Pollutants (COMEAP). *Statement on Update of Recommendations for Quantifying Hospital Admissions Associated with Short-Term Exposures to Air Pollutants*; COMEAP: Chilton, UK, 2021; pp. 1–14. Available online: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/air-pollution-quantifying-effects-on-hospital-admissions> (accessed on 11 December 2025).
44. Martins, L.M.; Coz, E.; Boulch, D.M.; Hacid, M.S. Machine Learning with Environmental Predictors to Forecast Hospital Visits and Admissions: A Systematic Review. *Environ. Syst. Res.* **2025**, *14*, 12. [[CrossRef](#)]
45. Labib, S.M. Greenness, air pollution, and temperature exposure effects in predicting premature mortality and morbidity: A small-area study using spatial random forest model. *Sci. Total Environ.* **2024**, *928*, 172387. [[CrossRef](#)]
46. Leirião, L.; de Oliveira, M.; Martins, T.; Miraglia, S. A Multi-Pollutant and Meteorological Analysis of Cardiorespiratory Mortality among the Elderly in São Paulo, Brazil—An Artificial Neural Networks Approach. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* **2023**, *20*, 5458. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
47. Leong, W.C.; Kelani, R.O.; Ahmad, Z. Prediction of air pollution index (API) using support vector machine (SVM). *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* **2020**, *8*, 103208. [[CrossRef](#)]
48. Xie, Q.; Ni, J.Q.; Li, E.; Bao, J.; Zheng, P. Sequential Air Pollution Emission Estimation Using a Hybrid Deep Learning Model and Health-Related Ventilation Control in a Pig Building. *J. Clean. Prod.* **2022**, *371*, 133714. [[CrossRef](#)]
49. Yan, X.; Zang, Z.; Luo, N.; Jiang, Y.; Li, Z. New Interpretable Deep Learning Model to Monitor Real-Time PM_{2.5} Concentrations from Satellite Data. *Environ. Int.* **2020**, *144*, 106060. [[CrossRef](#)]
50. Berrang-Ford, L.; Sietsma, A.J.; Callaghan, M.; Minx, J.C.; Scheelbeek, P.F.D.; Haddaway, N.R.; Haines, A.; Dangour, A.D. Systematic Mapping of Global Research on Climate and Health: A Machine Learning Review. *Lancet Planet. Health* **2021**, *5*, e514–e525. [[CrossRef](#)]
51. Temirbekov, N.; Temirbekova, M.; Tamabay, D.; Kasenov, S.; Askarov, S.; Tukenova, Z. Assessment of the Negative Impact of Urban Air Pollution on Population Health Using Machine Learning Method. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* **2023**, *20*, 6770. [[CrossRef](#)]
52. Abhadiomhen, S.E.; Nzeakor, E.O.; Oyibo, K. Health Risk Assessment Using Machine Learning: Systematic Review. *Electronics* **2024**, *13*, 4405. [[CrossRef](#)]
53. Mottahedin, P.; Chahkandi, B.; Moezzi, R.; Fathollahi-Fard, A.M.; Ghandali, M.; Gheibi, M. Air quality prediction and control systems using machine learning and adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system. *Heliyon* **2024**, *10*, e39783. [[CrossRef](#)]
54. Karmoude, M.; Munhungewarwa, B.; Chiraira, I.; Mckenzie, R.; Kong, J.; Smith, B.; Ayana, G.; Njara, N.; Mathaha, T.; Kumar, M.; et al. Machine learning for air quality prediction and data analysis: Review on recent advancements, challenges, and outlooks. *Sci. Total Environ.* **2025**, *1002*, 180593. [[CrossRef](#)]
55. Reid, C.E.; Jerrett, M.; Tager, I.B.; Petersen, M.L.; Mann, J.K.; Balmes, J.R. Differential Respiratory Health Effects from the 2008 Northern California Wildfires: A Spatiotemporal Approach. *Environ. Res.* **2016**, *150*, 227–235. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
56. Su, J.G.; Vuong, V.; Shahriary, E.; Aslebagh, S.; Yakutis, E.; Sage, E.; Haile, R.; Balmes, J.; Barrett, M. Health Effects of Air Pollution on Respiratory Symptoms: A Longitudinal Study Using Digital Health Sensors. *Environ. Int.* **2024**, *189*, 108810. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]

57. Wang, Y.; Chen, X.; Xue, F. A Review of Bayesian Spatiotemporal Models in Spatial Epidemiology. *ISPRS Int. J. Geoinf.* **2024**, *13*, 97. [[CrossRef](#)]
58. Teyton, A.; Baer, R.J.; Benmarhnia, T.; Bandoli, G. Exposure to Air Pollution and Emergency Department Visits during the First Year of Life among Preterm and Full-Term Infants. *JAMA Netw. Open* **2023**, *6*, E230262. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
59. Chou-Chen, S.W.; Barboza, L.A. Forecasting Hospital Discharges for Respiratory Conditions in Costa Rica Using Climate and Pollution Data. *Math. Biosci. Eng.* **2024**, *21*, 6539–6558. [[CrossRef](#)]
60. Wu, D.; Shi, Y.; Wang, C.C.; Li, C.; Lu, Y.; Wang, C.; Zhu, W.; Sun, T.; Han, J.; Zheng, Y.; et al. Investigating the Impact of Extreme Weather Events and Related Indicators on Cardiometabolic Multimorbidity. *Arch. Public Health* **2024**, *82*, 128. [[CrossRef](#)]
61. Luo, L.; Liao, C.; Zhang, F.; Zhang, W.; Li, C.; Qiu, Z.; Huang, D. Applicability of Internet Search Index for Asthma Admission Forecast Using Machine Learning. *Int. J. Health Plan. Manag.* **2018**, *33*, 723–732. [[CrossRef](#)]
62. Cappelli, F.; Castronuovo, G.; Grimaldi, S.; Telesca, V. Random Forest and Feature Importance Measures for Discriminating the Most Influential Environmental Factors in Predicting Cardiovascular and Respiratory Diseases. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* **2024**, *21*, 867. [[CrossRef](#)]
63. Chen, C.; Teyton, A.; Benmarhnia, T. The temporal trend and disparity in short-term health impacts of fine particulate matter in California (2006–2019). *Sci. Total Environ.* **2024**, *954*, 176543. [[CrossRef](#)]
64. Araz, O.M.; Olson, D.; Ramirez-Nafarrate, A. Predictive analytics for hospital admissions from the emergency department using triage information. *Int. J. Prod. Econ.* **2019**, *208*, 199–207. [[CrossRef](#)]
65. Gryech, I.; Asaad, C.; Ghogho, M.; Kobbane, A. Applications of Machine Learning & Internet of Things for Outdoor Air Pollution Monitoring and Prediction: A Systematic Literature Review. *Eng. Appl. Artif. Intell.* **2024**, *137*, 109182. [[CrossRef](#)]
66. Patel, P.; Patel, S.; Shah, K.; Desai, K.; Patel, S.; Shah, M.; Patel, S. A systematic study on PM2.5 and PM10 concentration prediction in air pollution using machine learning and deep learning model. *Environ. Chem. Ecotoxicol.* **2025**, *7*, 1401–1415. [[CrossRef](#)]
67. Zhu, Q.; Zhang, M.; Hu, Y.; Xu, X.; Tao, L.; Zhang, J.; Luo, Y.; Guo, X.; Liu, X. Research on Prediction of Daily Admissions of Respiratory Diseases with Comorbid Diabetes in Beijing Based on Long Short-Term Memory Recurrent Neural Network. *J. Zhejiang Univ. (Med. Sci.)* **2022**, *51*, 1–9. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
68. Yang, C.-T.; Chen, Y.-A.; Chan, Y.-W.; Lee, C.-L.; Tsan, Y.-T.; Chan, W.-C.; Liu, P.-Y. Influenza-like Illness Prediction Using a Long Short-Term Memory Deep Learning Model with Multiple Open Data Sources. *J. Supercomput.* **2020**, *76*, 9303–9329. [[CrossRef](#)]
69. Khatibi, T.; Karampour, N. Predicting the Number of Hospital Admissions Due to Mental Disorders from Air Pollutants and Weather Condition Descriptors Using Stacked Ensemble of Deep Convolutional Models and LSTM Models (SEDCMLM). *J. Clean. Prod.* **2021**, *280*, 124410. [[CrossRef](#)]
70. Araujo, L.N.; Belotti, J.T.; Alves, T.A.; Tadano, Y.d.S.; Siqueira, H. Ensemble Method Based on Artificial Neural Networks to Estimate Air Pollution Health Risks. *Environ. Model. Softw.* **2020**, *123*, 104567. [[CrossRef](#)]
71. Zhou, L.; Zhu, Q.; Chen, Q.; Wang, P.; Huang, H. Predicting Hospital Outpatient Volume Using XGBoost: A Machine Learning Approach. *Sci. Rep.* **2025**, *15*, 17028. [[CrossRef](#)]
72. Bellinger, C.; Mohamed Jabbar, M.S.; Zaiane, O.; Osornio-Vargas, A. A Systematic Review of Data Mining and Machine Learning for Air Pollution Epidemiology. *BMC Public Health* **2017**, *17*, 907. [[CrossRef](#)]
73. Manisalidis, I.; Stavropoulou, E.; Stavropoulos, A.; Bezirtzoglou, E. Environmental and Health Impacts of Air Pollution: A Review. *Front. Public Health* **2020**, *8*, 14. [[CrossRef](#)]
74. Yang, J.; Xu, X.; Ma, X.; Wang, Z.; You, Q.; Shan, W.; Yang, Y.; Bo, X.; Yin, C. Application of Machine Learning to Predict Hospital Visits for Respiratory Diseases Using Meteorological and Air Pollution Factors in Linyi, China. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* **2023**, *30*, 88431–88443. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
75. Li, Y.C.; Hsu, H.H.L.; Chun, Y.; Chiu, P.H.; Arditi, Z.; Claudio, L.; Pandey, G.; Bunyavanich, S. Machine Learning-Driven Identification of Early-Life Air Toxic Combinations Associated with Childhood Asthma Outcomes. *J. Clin. Investig.* **2021**, *131*, e152088. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
76. Kristiani, E.; Chen, Y.A.; Yang, C.T.; Huang, C.Y.; Tsan, Y.T.; Chan, W.C. Using Deep Ensemble for Influenza-like Illness Consultation Rate Prediction. *Future Gener. Comput. Syst.* **2021**, *117*, 369–386. [[CrossRef](#)]
77. Da Silva Bonifácio, A.; de Lima Brum, R.; Tavella, R.A.; They, N.H.; Nadaleti, W.C.; Coronas, M.V.; Saes-Silva, E.; Brum, A.N.; Buffarini, R.; Félix Correia Filho, W.L.; et al. Health Impact Assessment of Air Pollutants in Simulated Temperature Scenarios in the Largest Coal Mining Region of Brazil. *Case Stud. Chem. Environ. Eng.* **2024**, *10*, 100923. [[CrossRef](#)]
78. Li, Z.; Lv, S.; Lu, F.; Guo, M.; Wu, Z.; Liu, Y.; Li, W.; Liu, M.; Yu, S.; Jiang, Y.; et al. Causal Associations of Air Pollution With Cardiovascular Disease and Respiratory Diseases Among Elder Diabetic Patients. *Geohealth* **2023**, *7*, e2022GH000730. [[CrossRef](#)]
79. Alari, A.; Ranzani, O.; Olmos, S.; Milà, C.; Rico, A.; Ballester, J.; Basagaña, X.; Dadvand, P.; Duarte-Salles, T.; Nieuwenhuijsen, M.; et al. Short-Term Exposure to Air Pollution and Hospital Admission after COVID-19 in Catalonia: The COVAIR-CAT Study. *Int. J. Epidemiol.* **2024**, *53*, dyae041. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]

80. Dashtaki, N.M.; Mirahmadizadeh, A.; Fararouei, M.; Dashtaki, R.M.; Hoseini, M.; Nayeb, M.R. The Lag-Effects of Air Pollutants and Meteorological Factors on COVID-19 Infection Transmission and Severity: Using Machine Learning Techniques. *J. Res. Health Sci.* **2024**, *24*, e00622. [[CrossRef](#)]
81. Mun, S.K.; Chang, M. Development of Prediction Models for the Incidence of Pediatric Acute Otitis Media Using Poisson Regression Analysis and XGBoost. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* **2022**, *29*, 18629–18640. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
82. Usmani, R.S.A.; Pillai, T.R.; Hashem, I.A.T.; Marjani, M.; Shaharudin, R.; Latif, M.T. Air Pollution and Cardiorespiratory Hospitalization, Predictive Modeling, and Analysis Using Artificial Intelligence Techniques. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* **2021**, *28*, 56759–56771. [[CrossRef](#)]
83. Hayet-Otero, M.; García-García, F.; Lee, D.J.; Martínez-Minaya, J.; Yandiola, P.P.E.; Landa, I.U.; Ermecheo, M.N.; Quintana, J.M.; Menéndez, R.; Torres, A.; et al. Extracting Relevant Predictive Variables for COVID-19 Severity Prognosis: An Exhaustive Comparison of Feature Selection Techniques. *PLoS ONE* **2023**, *18*, e0284150. [[CrossRef](#)]
84. Chen, G.; Wang, A.; Li, S.; Zhao, X.; Wang, Y.; Li, H.; Meng, X.; Knibbs, L.D.; Bell, M.L.; Abramson, M.J.; et al. Long-Term Exposure to Air Pollution and Survival after Ischemic Stroke: The China National Stroke Registry Cohort. *Stroke* **2019**, *50*, 563–570. [[CrossRef](#)]
85. Madani, N.A.; Jones, L.E.; Carpenter, D.O. Different Volatile Organic Compounds in Local Point Source Air Pollution Pose Distinctive Elevated Risks for Respiratory Disease-Associated Emergency Room Visits. *Chemosphere* **2023**, *344*, 140403. [[CrossRef](#)]
86. Rybarczyk, Y.; Zalakeviciute, R. Machine Learning Approaches for Outdoor Air Quality Modelling: A Systematic Review. *Appl. Sci.* **2018**, *8*, 2570. [[CrossRef](#)]
87. Agbehadji, I.E.; Obagbuwa, I.C. Systematic Review of Machine Learning and Deep Learning Techniques for Spatiotemporal Air Quality Prediction. *Atmosphere* **2024**, *15*, 1352. [[CrossRef](#)]
88. Castronuovo, G.; Favia, G.; Telesca, V.; Vammacigno, A. Analyzing the Interactions between Environmental Parameters and Cardiovascular Diseases Using Random Forest and SHAP Algorithms. *Rev. Cardiovasc. Med.* **2023**, *24*, 330. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
89. Vachon, J.; Kerckhoffs, J.; Buteau, S.; Smargiassi, A. Do Machine Learning Methods Improve Prediction of Ambient Air Pollutants with High Spatial Contrast? A Systematic Review. *Environ. Res.* **2024**, *262*, 119751. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
90. Chadalavada, S.; Faust, O.; Salvi, M.; Seoni, S.; Raj, N.; Raghavendra, U.; Gudigar, A.; Barua, P.D.; Molinari, F.; Acharya, R. Application of Artificial Intelligence in Air Pollution Monitoring and Forecasting: A Systematic Review. *Environ. Model. Softw.* **2025**, *185*, 106312. [[CrossRef](#)]
91. Xayasouk, T.; Lee, H.; Lee, G. Air Pollution Prediction Using Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) and Deep Autoencoder (DAE) Models. *Sustainability* **2020**, *12*, 2570. [[CrossRef](#)]
92. Liu, Y.; Guo, M.; Wang, J.; Gong, Y.; Huang, C.; Wang, W.; Liu, X.; Liu, J.; Ju, C.; Ba, Y.; et al. Effect of Short-Term Exposure to Air Pollution on Hospital Admission for Cardiovascular Disease: A Time-Series Study in Xiangyang, China. *Sci. Total Environ.* **2024**, *918*, 170735. [[CrossRef](#)]
93. Tavera Busso, I.; Rodríguez Núñez, M.; Amarillo, A.C.; Mettan, F.; Carreras, H.A. Modeling Air Pollution-Related Hospital Admissions Employing Remote Sensing and Geographical Information Systems. *Atmos. Environ.* **2021**, *261*, 118502. [[CrossRef](#)]
94. Danesh Yazdi, M.; Wang, Y.; Di, Q.; Wei, Y.; Requia, W.J.; Shi, L.; Sabath, M.B.; Dominici, F.; Coull, B.A.; Evans, J.S.; et al. Long-Term Association of Air Pollution and Hospital Admissions among Medicare Participants Using a Doubly Robust Additive Model. *Circulation* **2021**, *143*, 1584–1596. [[CrossRef](#)]
95. Qiu, H.; Luo, L.; Su, Z.; Zhou, L.; Wang, L.; Chen, Y. Machine Learning Approaches to Predict Peak Demand Days of Cardiovascular Admissions Considering Environmental Exposure. *BMC Med. Inform. Decis. Mak.* **2020**, *20*, 83. [[CrossRef](#)]
96. Tony Cox, L.A.; Liu, X.; Shi, L.; Zu, K.; Goodman, J. Applying Nonparametric Methods to Analyses of Short-Term Fine Particulate Matter Exposure and Hospital Admissions for Cardiovascular Diseases among Older Adults. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* **2017**, *14*, 1051. [[CrossRef](#)]
97. Achebak, H.; Rey, G.; Chen, Z.Y.; Lloyd, S.J.; Quijal-Zamorano, M.; Méndez-Turrubiates, R.F.; Ballester, J. Heat Exposure and Cause-Specific Hospital Admissions in Spain: A Nationwide Cross-Sectional Study. *Environ. Health Perspect.* **2024**, *132*, 57009. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
98. Lary, D.J.; Lary, T.; Sattler, B. Using Machine Learning to Estimate Global PM_{2.5} for Environmental Health Studies. *Environ. Health Insights* **2015**, *9*, 41–52. [[CrossRef](#)]
99. Wu, J.; Dai, Q.; Song, S. Optimizing BenMAP health impact assessment with meteorological factor driven machine learning models. *Sci. Total Environ.* **2024**, *949*, 175246. [[CrossRef](#)]
100. Peng, J.; Chen, C.; Zhou, M.; Xie, X.; Zhou, Y.; Luo, C.H. Peak Outpatient and Emergency Department Visit Forecasting for Patients with Chronic Respiratory Diseases Using Machine Learning Methods: Retrospective Cohort Study. *JMIR Med. Inform.* **2020**, *8*, e13075. [[CrossRef](#)]
101. Rackow, B.; König, H.-H.; Wall, M.; Konnopka, C. The interaction between air pollution, weather conditions, and health risks: A systematic review. *Sci. Total Environ.* **2025**, *996*, 180080. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]

102. Klompmaker, J.O.; Janssen, N.A.H.; Bloemsmma, L.D.; Gehring, U.; Wijga, A.H.; van den Brink, C.; Lebret, E.; Brunekreef, B.; Hoek, G. Residential Surrounding Green, Air Pollution, Traffic Noise and Self-Perceived General Health. *Environ. Res.* **2019**, *179*, 108751. [[CrossRef](#)]
103. Hoek, G.; Beelen, R.; de Hoogh, K.; Vienneau, D.; Gulliver, J.; Fischer, P.; Briggs, D. A Review of Land-Use Regression Models to Assess Spatial Variation of Outdoor Air Pollution. *Atmos. Environ.* **2008**, *42*, 7561–7578. [[CrossRef](#)]
104. Anggraini, T.S.; Irie, H.; Sakti, A.D.; Wikantika, K. Machine learning-based global air quality index development using remote sensing and ground-based stations. *Environ. Adv.* **2024**, *15*, 100456. [[CrossRef](#)]
105. Wei, Y.; Qiu, X.; Sabath, M.B.; Yazdi, M.D.; Yin, K.; Li, L.; Peralta, A.A.; Wang, C.; Koutrakis, P.; Zanobetti, A.; et al. Air Pollutants and Asthma Hospitalization in the Medicaid Population. *Am. J. Respir. Crit. Care Med.* **2022**, *205*, 1075–1083. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
106. Kassomenos, P.; Petrakis, M.; Sarigiannis, D.; Gotti, A.; Karakitsios, S. Identifying the Contribution of Physical and Chemical Stressors to the Daily Number of Hospital Admissions Implementing an Artificial Neural Network Model. *Air Qual. Atmos. Health* **2011**, *4*, 263–272. [[CrossRef](#)]
107. Kansagara, D.; Englander, H.; Salanitro, A.; Kagen, D.; Theobald, C.; Freeman, M.; Kripalani, S. Risk Prediction Models for Hospital Readmission. *JAMA* **2011**, *306*, 1688. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
108. Wei, Y.; Amini, H.; Qiu, X.; Castro, E.; Jin, T.; Yin, K.; Vu, B.N.; Healy, J.; Feng, Y.; Zhang, J.; et al. Grouped Mixtures of Air Pollutants and Seasonal Temperature Anomalies and Cardiovascular Hospitalizations among U.S. Residents. *Environ. Int.* **2024**, *187*, 108651. [[CrossRef](#)]
109. Ravindra, K.; Bahadur, S.S.; Katoch, V.; Bhardwaj, S.; Kaur-Sidhu, M.; Gupta, M.; Mor, S. Application of Machine Learning Approaches to Predict the Impact of Ambient Air Pollution on Outpatient Visits for Acute Respiratory Infections. *Sci. Total Environ.* **2023**, *858*, 159509. [[CrossRef](#)]
110. Moustiris, K.P.; Douros, K.; Nastos, P.T.; Larissi, I.K.; Anthracopoulos, M.B.; Paliatsos, A.G.; Priftis, K.N. Seven-Days-Ahead Forecasting of Childhood Asthma Admissions Using Artificial Neural Networks in Athens, Greece. *Int. J. Environ. Health Res.* **2012**, *22*, 93–104. [[CrossRef](#)]
111. Dianat, M.S.I.; Jafarabadi, M.A. Air Pollution and Hospital Admissions for Cardiorespiratory Diseases in Iran: Artificial Neural Network versus Conditional Logistic Regression. *Int. J. Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2015**, *12*, 3433–3442. [[CrossRef](#)]
112. Zhalehdoost, A.; Taleai, M. Unravelling the importance of spatial and temporal resolutions in modeling urban air pollution using a machine learning approach. *Sci. Rep.* **2025**, *15*, 27708. [[CrossRef](#)]
113. Gafni-Pappas, G.; Khan, M. Predicting daily emergency department visits using machine learning could increase accuracy. *Am. J. Emerg. Med.* **2023**, *65*, 5–11. [[CrossRef](#)]
114. Ram, S.; Zhang, W.; Williams, M.; Pengetnze, Y. Predicting Asthma-Related Emergency Department Visits Using Big Data. *IEEE J. Biomed. Health Inform.* **2015**, *19*, 1216–1223. [[CrossRef](#)]
115. Ryu, B.; Yoo, S.; Kim, S.; Choi, J. Thirty-Day Hospital Readmission Prediction Model Based on Common Data Model with Weather and Air Quality Data. *Sci. Rep.* **2021**, *11*, 23313. [[CrossRef](#)]
116. Elser, H.; Rowland, S.T.; Marek, M.S.; Kiang, M.V.; Shea, B.; Do, V.; Benmarhnia, T.; Schneider, A.L.C.; Casey, J.A. Wildfire Smoke Exposure and Emergency Department Visits for Headache: A Case-Crossover Analysis in California, 2006–2020. *Headache* **2023**, *63*, 94–103. [[CrossRef](#)]
117. Gogna, P.; Borghese, M.M.; Villeneuve, P.J.; Kumarathasan, P.; Johnson, M.; Shutt, R.H.; Ashley-Martin, J.; Bouchard, M.F.; King, W.D. A cohort study of the multipollutant effects of PM_{2.5}, NO₂, and O₃ on C-reactive protein levels during pregnancy. *Environ. Epidemiol.* **2024**, *8*, e308. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
118. Dos Reis, J.S.; Costa, R.L.; dos Silva, F.D.S.; de Souza, E.D.F.; Cortes, T.R.; Coelho, R.H.; Velasco, S.R.M.; Neves, D.J.D.; Sousa Filho, J.F.; Barreto, C.E.C.; et al. Predicting Asthma Hospitalizations from Climate and Air Pollution Data: A Machine Learning-Based Approach. *Climate* **2025**, *13*, 23. [[CrossRef](#)]
119. Albadrani, M. Socioeconomic Disparities in Mortality from Indoor Air Pollution: A Multi-Country Study. *PLoS ONE* **2025**, *20*, e0317581. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
120. Cabral-Miranda, W.; Beloni, C.; Lora, F.; Afonso, R.; Araújo, T.; Fernandes, F. Artificial Intelligence Platform to Predict Children’s Hospital Care for Respiratory Disease Using Clinical, Pollution, and Climatic Factors. *J. Glob. Health* **2025**, *15*, 04207. [[CrossRef](#)]
121. Lee, S.; Hyun, C.; Lee, M. Machine Learning Big Data Analysis of the Impact of Air Pollutants on Rhinitis-Related Hospital Visits. *Toxics* **2023**, *11*, 719. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
122. Lee, S.; Ku, H.; Hyun, C.; Lee, M. Machine Learning-Based Analyses of the Effects of Various Types of Air Pollutants on Hospital Visits by Asthma Patients. *Toxics* **2022**, *10*, 644. [[CrossRef](#)]
123. Kananura, R.M. Machine Learning Predictive Modelling for Identification of Predictors of Acute Respiratory Infection and Diarrhoea in Uganda’s Rural and Urban Settings. *PLoS Glob. Public Health* **2022**, *2*, e0000430. [[CrossRef](#)]
124. Fenta, H.M.; Zewotir, T.T.; Naidoo, S.; Naidoo, R.N.; Mwambi, H. Factors of Acute Respiratory Infection among Under-Five Children across Sub-Saharan African Countries Using Machine Learning Approaches. *Sci. Rep.* **2024**, *14*, 15801. [[CrossRef](#)]

125. Orchard, P.; Agakova, A.; Pinnock, H.; Burton, C.D.; Sarran, C.; Agakov, F.; McKinstry, B. Improving Prediction of Risk of Hospital Admission in Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease: Application of Machine Learning to Telemonitoring Data. *J. Med. Internet Res.* **2018**, *20*, e263. [[CrossRef](#)]
126. Ameer, S.; Shah, M.A.; Khan, A.; Song, H.; Maple, C.; Islam, S.U.; Asghar, M.N. Comparative Analysis of Machine Learning Techniques for Predicting Air Quality in Smart Cities. *IEEE Access* **2019**, *7*, 128325–128338. [[CrossRef](#)]
127. Strak, M.; Janssen, N.; Beelen, R.; Schmitz, O.; Karssenberg, D.; Houthuijs, D.; van den Brink, C.; Dijst, M.; Brunekreef, B.; Hoek, G. Associations between lifestyle and air pollution exposure: Potential for confounding in large administrative data cohorts. *Environ. Res.* **2017**, *156*, 364–373. [[CrossRef](#)]
128. Reid, C.E.; Considine, E.M.; Watson, G.L.; Telesca, D.; Pfister, G.G.; Jerrett, M. Associations between Respiratory Health and Ozone and Fine Particulate Matter during a Wildfire Event. *Environ. Int.* **2019**, *129*, 291–298. [[CrossRef](#)]
129. Zhixu, H.U.; Qiu, H.; Su, Z.; Shen, M.; Chen, Z. A Stacking Ensemble Model to Predict Daily Number of Hospital Admissions for Cardiovascular Diseases. *Digit. Object Identifier* **2020**, *8*, 138719–138729. [[CrossRef](#)]
130. Sciannameo, V.; Goffi, A.; Maffei, G.; Gianfreda, R.; Jahier Pagliari, D.; Filippini, T.; Mancuso, P.; Giorgi-Rossi, P.; Alberto Dal Zovo, L.; Corbari, A.; et al. A Deep Learning Approach for Spatio-Temporal Forecasting of New Cases and New Hospital Admissions of COVID-19 Spread in Reggio Emilia, Northern Italy. *J. Biomed. Inform.* **2022**, *132*, 104132. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]

Disclaimer/Publisher’s Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of MDPI and/or the editor(s). MDPI and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.